

What's next

The first stage of the project, focusing on collecting information from society about their perspectives and knowledge on ART as well as from clinics regarding their current services and approach, is coming to an end, opening the path for the second stage:

Three main objectives compose the second stage:

1. To compare views of the general public with the information provided by clinics;
2. To assess their alignment from gender, socio-cultural, and legal perspectives;
3. To produce national guidelines that identify concrete research goals needed to make ART better aligned with society's needs, expectations, and values.

B2-InF's gender content analysis will specifically focus on gender differences concerning values and opinions related to different decision capacities and opinions regarding gender differences in the responsibility of ART clinics and ART users.

During the second stage, the project will try to go beyond the fundamental male/female dichotomy and also investigate, where possible, representations of and information about transgender and intersex populations, as they are becoming increasingly involved with ART technologies.

In addition to the above, this stage will also compare the results of stage one concerning socio-cultural analysis, focusing on the following activities:

- To observe how young people approach ART (Is it a scientific advance or a sociological threat? The socio-cultural references and values mobilized to justify their representations?).
- To evaluate the sociodemographic and socio-cultural characteristics that impact ART knowledge, awareness, and representations. (Do family situations, religion, economic status, education level, or origins play a role in how ART is known, perceived and judged?)
- To identify expectations regarding ART among young nationals that conform to or diverge from dominant representations (statistically speaking, or the most accepted/tolerated) in each selected country.

B2-InF legal analysis is interested in analyzing Social Perceptions of ART and its relationship to ART's legal and case law regulations, including soft law, at national, EU and third-country levels. B2-InF will also do a legal revision of the Information about ART.

The second stage of the project will last sixteen months.